

PHOTOCHEMICAL STUDIES ON URANYL SALTS

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Under the above title, S. K. Bhattacharya and Sharda Gulvady (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 654) have studied the photochemical oxidation of ethyl alcohol, lactic acid and mandelic acid by uranyl nitrate. These authors have stated that the reaction is zero-molecular with respect to the aldehyde formed in each case. From a purely kinetic point of view, the idea of zero-molecularity with respect to the aldehyde formed is fictitious. This zero-molecularity will disappear if the concentration of the reductant taken is less or approximately equal to that of uranyl nitrate taken.

As a matter of fact, these authors have failed to appreciate the kinetic significance of the data obtained by them. These results clearly indicate that the reaction is zero-molecular with respect to uranyl nitrate, and as long as the concentration of the reductant is great (*i.e.* can be taken as constant) as compared to uranyl salt, the formation of aldehyde will show a zero-molecular character. In all other cases, the rate of formation of aldehyde will vary right from the beginning to the end of the reaction. The only case where the concentration of reductant is less than that of the oxidant is the first experiment of Table VII (*loc. cit.* p. 654) where the concentration of the reductant is $17.4 \times 10^{-3} M$ and that of uranyl nitrate is $20 \times 10^{-3} M$. We are sure that in this particular experiment, the $\Delta x / \Delta t$ will not show a constant character. As a matter of fact, $\Delta x / \Delta t$ in this experiment is meaningless and cannot be identified (this identification being valid in zero-molecular reaction) with the instantaneous velocity (*i.e.* dx/dt) of the reaction. This $\Delta x / \Delta t$ must be an average value, but this fact has not been mentioned by the authors.

However, there appears to be one reason which has prevented the authors from ascribing zero-molecularity to uranyl nitrate. They find that the velocity depends upon the concentration of uranyl nitrate, but they have missed the important fact that it is only the increased intensity of absorbed radiation which is material in bringing about an enhancement in the velocity of the reaction. If we keep the intensity of the absorbed radiation constant (for a particular frequency, and concentration of the reductant) and vary the concentration of uranyl nitrate, no variation in the velocity constant will be observed, *i.e.*, it will be independent of the concentration of uranyl nitrate. This fact is obvious from their data, where for the intensity of light absorbed being the same viz., 7.5×10^{-13} , the velocity constant of the reaction between lactic acid and uranyl nitrate is 7.7×10^{-10} , when the concentration of uranyl nitrate is $20 \times 10^{-3} M$ and it is 7.5×10^{-10} , when the concentration of the nitrate is halved. Consequently the reaction is zero-molecular with respect to uranyl nitrate. The total order is less than unity and greater than zero.

